

EVALUATION OF ANTIOXIDANT AND ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF APPLE CIDER VINEGAR

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ABSTRACT

Background: Apple cider vinegar is a popular natural substance with a long history of health benefits and medicinal possibilities. Apple cider vinegar was used as a stomachic, carminative, appetite regulator, hypoglycaemia effect, weight management assistance, astringent, and general health tonic in the traditional medical system. It may also have antibacterial and antioxidant properties. Although microorganisms are an essential component of our intestines and buccal cavity, abnormal microflora can lead to clinical symptoms. **Objective:** The current study attempts to evaluate the antioxidant activity of different concentration of apple cider vinegar using in-vitro methods and the efficacy of different concentration of apple cider vinegar against Gram-negative bacteria. **Methods:** The apple cider vinegar were subjected to phytochemical screening

and in-vitro antioxidant and antimicrobial tests. DPPH radical scavenging, nitric oxide scavenging, and reducing power absorbance were measured in order to assess the antioxidant activity of various concentrations (100–500 µg/ml). The four bacterial strains of microorganisms are chosen after agar media is prepared for the assessment of antioxidant and antibacterial properties. Three different concentrations of apple cider vinegar (50, 100, and 200 µg/ml) were utilized for the antibacterial susceptibility tests, which were conducted using the usual well diffusion method. **Results:** The different concentration of apple cider vinegar (10%, 20% and 40%) showed appreciable DPPH free radical scavenging, reducing power, and

nitric oxide inhibitory activities with a concentration-dependent increase in their effects. *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus vulgaris*, and *Salmonella typhi* growth were suppressed by the different concentration of apple cider vinegar. With a zone of inhibition of 20.9 mm, ACV (40%) demonstrated the highest level of efficacy against *S. typhi*. **Conclusion:** According to the study's findings, apple cider vinegar has strong antimicrobial and antioxidant properties.

KEYWORDS: Antioxidant, Antimicrobial, Apple Cider Vinegar.

1. INTRODUCTION

Microbial disorders have had a devastating effect on human history since time immemorial. The loss of human life due to some notorious pathogens (e.g., *Vibrio cholera*, *Salmonella typhi*) has prompted the development of antibiotics and other anti-microbial agents. However, non-rational and extensive use of antibiotics has caused the emergence of resistant microorganisms and increased chances of adverse events.^[1] There are narrow- and broad-spectrum antimicrobials/antibiotics to treat microbial diseases.^[2] However, many restrictions over the use of antimicrobials/antibiotics exist because of their age, comorbidity (e.g., diabetes), and time-related side effects which are mainly related to gastric problems (for example – nausea, diarrhea, vomiting, stomach upset, lack of appetite), disruption of gut flora by broad-spectrum antimicrobials, hypersensitivity reactions, blood, hepatic and renal side effects.^[1,2] Hence, there is a need to shift the focus from synthetic or semi-synthetic antibiotics/antimicrobials toward natural and ayurvedic drugs.^[3] Furthermore, quite a few secondary metabolites present in medicinal plants might serve as potent anti-oxidants and anti-inflammatory agents which can be exploited in different disorders and also supplement the antimicrobial activity.^[4] The apple, or *Malus domestica*, is the second most popular fruit in the world. It is a pomaceous fruit species that is a member of the Rosaceae family. Apples make up a substantial portion of the human diet and are a natural source of phenolic compounds and dietary phytochemicals.^[5] Apple polyphenols and oligomeric proanthocyanidins are the primary sources of its antioxidant activity.^[6] *Malus domestica* has a high concentration of antioxidants, which may help prevent oxidative stress, according to in vitro experiments. As a result, apple cider vinegar may have antibacterial qualities and be helpful in regulating the immune response on the mucosal and systemic levels.^[7] Apple cider vinegar (ACV), which is made by fermenting apple juice that contains various organic acids and compounds, is widely used in Chinese food preparation due to its unique fruity tone,

which is counterbalanced by its acidity.^[8,9] In essence, vinegar fermentation is a two-step process: first, fermentable sugars are converted to ethanol by yeasts, typically *Saccharomyces* species, and second, ethanol is oxidized to acetic acid by bacteria, typically *Acetobacter* species.^[10,11] For around 5000 years, flavoured vinegar has been manufactured and marketed as a commercial commodity.^[12,13]

In light of the foregoing findings, the current study attempts to evaluate the antioxidant activity of different concentration of apple cider vinegar using in-vitro methods. We also evaluated the efficacy of different concentration of apple cider vinegar against Gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus vulgaris*, and, *Salmonella typhi*.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The apple cider vinegar was purchased from Mohali, Punjab, India, from authenticated sources.

2.1 Preparation of Apple Cider Vinegar

Red delicious apples are used to produce natural apple cider vinegar with inclusion of maceration. The fresh fruits were washed and the cores and peels of apples are separated. It is important to pick up organic apples so that will get the full benefits of apple cider vinegar. Glass jar was selected and to this warm water, apple pieces and organic sugar was added and stirred well. Later covered the jar with a cotton cloth and put a rubber band around it and stored the glass jar in a cool and dry place. Allowed it to stand for 2 to 3 weeks so that fermentation takes place. During this period stirring of apple cider vinegar is done. This is very important step because it will help in fermentation process. On 27th day the peels are separated and filtered the liquid and tested for acidity of apple cider vinegar.

2.2 Qualitative phytochemical analysis

A stock concentration of 1% apple cider vinegar was prepared by using water as solvent. These apple cider vinegars were tested for the presence of active phytochemicals viz: tannins, alkaloids, phytosterols, triterpenoids, flavonoids, cardiac glycosides, anthraquinone glycosides, saponins, carbohydrates, proteins, amino acids, fixed oils and fats following standard methods.^[14]

2.3 Determining Antioxidant Activity

2.3.1. 2, 2-Diphenyl-1-Picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) assay

The free radical scavenging capacity or electron donating ability of different concentration of Apple cider vinegar was determined using DPPH. DPPH (0.04% w/v) solution was freshly prepared in 95% methanol. Different concentrations (100 to 500 µg/ml) of apple cider vinegar were prepared. 0.1 ml of the various concentrations of above-mentioned apple cider vinegar were mixed with 1.0 ml of DPPH solution. The reaction mixture was incubated in dark for 30 min. The absorbance was measured at 517 nm. Ascorbic acid was used as a standard (1 mg/ml). All the tests were performed in triplicate. The scavenging ability of the different concentration apple cider vinegar and ascorbic acid was calculated using this equation

$$\text{DPPH scavenging activity (\%)} = \frac{(\text{Abs.C} - \text{Abs.S})}{(\text{Abs.C})} \times 100.$$

Where, Abs. C is the absorbance of DPPH + methanol

Abs.S is the absorbance of DPPH radical + sample (i.e. apple cider vinegar or standard).

2.3.2. Determination of reducing power

This method was based on the reduction of the Fe (III)/ferricyanide complex to the ferrous form by one-electron-donating antioxidant. The reducing power was determined according to the method of Oyaizu. Aliquots (2.5 ml) of different concentrations of apple cider vinegar (100- 500 µg/ml) were mixed with 2.5 ml phosphate buffer (0.2 M, pH=6.6) and 2.5 ml potassium ferricyanide (1 %), followed by incubation at 50 °C for 20 min in dark. After incubation, 2.5 ml of TCA (10 %) was added to terminate the reaction and the mixture was subjected to centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 10 min. The upper layer (2.5 ml) was mixed with 2.5 ml of deionized water and 0.5 ml of 0.1% ferric chloride. The reaction mixture was incubated for 10 min at room temperature and the absorbance was measured at 700 nm against an appropriate blank solution. All tests were run in triplicate. Ascorbic acid as positive control was also tested for the reducing power assay in similar manner.

2.3.3. Nitric oxide radical inhibition assay

The Nitric oxide scavenging activity of different concentration of apple cider vinegar was determined according to the standard method. In this assay, the solution of 2 ml SNP (10 mM) in 0.5 ml phosphate buffer saline (PBS, pH=7.4) was mixed with 0.5 ml different concentrations of apple cider vinegar (100-500 µg/ml), and the mixture was incubated at 37 °C for 60 min in light. The half quantity of aliquots was taken and mixed with equal quantity

of Griess reagent, and the mixture was incubated at 25⁰C for 30 min in dark. The absorbance of pink color chromophore, generated during diazotization of nitric ions with sulphanilamide and subsequent coupling with naphthyl ethylene diaminedihydrochloride, was read at 546 nm against a blank sample. All the tests were performed in triplicate. Ascorbic acid was used as the reference compound in same concentration range.

2.4 Evaluation of antimicrobial activity

The first and foremost steps for evaluation of antimicrobial activity of Apple cider vinegar were to sterilize all the glassware in an autoclave at 15 psi at 12°C for 20 minutes. After sterilization the subsequent steps followed

- Preparation of media.
- Selection of the test microorganisms.
- Performing the sensitivity tests of Apple cider vinegar for anti-microbial activity.

2.4.1. Anti-microbial activity

Following microbial strains were used to evaluate the antimicrobial activity of Apple cider vinegar.

- *Escherichia coli*.
- *Salmonella typhi*.
- *Proteus vulgaris*.
- *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

The above-mentioned gram-negative bacterial strains were grown on nutrient agar plates at 37 °C and maintained on mueller hintont agar slants at 25 °C.

Nutrient medium used: Muller hinton agar medium.

Preparation of muller hinton agar medium

The medium was prepared by dissolving 38 g of the commercially available muller hinton agar medium (Himedia) in 1000 ml of distilled water. The dissolved medium was autoclaved at 15 lbs pressure at 121 °C for 15 minutes. The autoclaved medium was cooled to 45-50 °C, mixed well and poured in 100 mm petriplates (20-25 ml/plate).

Standard used: Streptomycin disc (antibacterial agent).

Preparation of inoculums

The stock cultures were sub cultured on the fresh muller hinton agar media and incubated for 24 hours at 37 °C. The fresh culture was then inoculated into 25 ml of MHA medium and incubated for 24 hours at 37 °C.

Preparation of test solution

1. 10% concentration of apple cider vinegar.
2. 20% concentration of apple cider vinegar.
3. 40% concentration of apple cider vinegar.

2.4.2. Antimicrobial assay

To check the presence of antimicrobial substance, the antimicrobial susceptibility tests were performed by standard well diffusion method. Antimicrobial assay for different concentration of apple cider vinegar was performed by agar well diffusion method as described by 100 µl of standardized inoculum of each test bacterium was inoculated on molten mueller hinton agar (Himedia), homogenised and then poured into sterile petri plates to yield a uniform depth of 4 mm. The petriplates were allowed to solidify inside the laminar hood. Sterile cork borers of 4 mm in diameter were used to make uniform wells into each petri plate. 50 µl of each concentration (50 µg/ml, 100 µg/ml and 200 µg/ml) of apple cider vinegar, prepared in aqueous solvent. Streptomycin (10 µg/ml) disc was placed at the centre of each petriplate and served as positive control, while as 10% dimethylsulfoxide served as negative control. The petri plates were then incubated at 37 °C for 18 to 24 hours in an incubator. The plates were then observed for the zones of inhibition. Antibacterial potential was evaluated by measuring the diameters of zones of inhibition in millimeters (mm) with the help of a standard measuring scale.

Determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration

The “minimum inhibitory concentration” (MIC) of apple cider vinegar was evaluated using 96-well microplates.^[15] Different concentration of apple cider vinegar (10%,20% and 40%) were prepared and used as test sample. Initially 50 µL of Mueller Hinton broth (MHB) was added to each well or bore. Then 150 µL of ACV solution was added to the 1st column of the microplate to obtain the desired starting concentration. A two-fold serial dilution was made initiating from the first column to the tenth column to achieve arrange of decreasing ACV concentration. From the last column, 50 µL of the mixture was discarded to maintain equal volume across all wells. A standardised bacterial suspension was prepared and 50 µL was

added to each well under aseptic conditions. Afterward, the microplates were incubated (temp 37°C) for a 24 h period. MIC was assessed by the addition of 30 µL of 0.02% p-iodonitrotetrazolium chloride (INT) (2 mg/mL) and then incubated (temp 37°C) for a 32 min duration. INT indicated bacterial progress by a colour change to pink. No change in colour post INT addition in the wells indicated nil growth of the microorganisms. The lowest concentration of ACV that completely inhibited visible bacterial growth was recorded as the MIC.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Preliminary phytochemical screening tests

The results of preliminary phytochemical screening conduct on the different concentration of Apple cider vinegar are shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Result of Preliminary phytochemical screening of different concentration of Apple cider vinegar.

S. No.	Phytochemical tests	ACV (10%)	ACV (20%)	ACV (40%)
1	Test for Alkaloids			
	Dragendroffs test	-	-	-
	Hagers test	-	-	-
	Wagners test	-	-	-
2	Test for triterpenoids			
	Salkawaski test	-	-	-
3	Test for Phyto sterols			
	Liebermann Buchard's test	-	-	-
	Salkowski test	-	-	-
4	Test for Flavonoids			
	Shinoda test	+	+	++
	Alkaline reagent test	+	+	++
	Lead acetate test	+	+	++
5	Test for Saponins			
	Foam test	-	-	-
	Olive oil stain test	-	-	-
6	Test for glycosides			
	Keller Killani test	-	-	-
7	Test for anthraquinone glycosides	-	-	-
8	Test for phenolic compounds	+	++	++
9	Test for Proteins			
	Biuret test	-	-	-
10	Test for Amino acids			
	Millions test	-	-	-
	Ninhydrin test	-	-	-

	Xanthoproteic test	-	-	-
	Paulys test	-	-	-
11	Test for Carbohydrate			
	Molish test	+	+	+
	Barfoeds test	-	-	-
	Seliwanoffs test	±	+	+

+ Present : - Absent

3.2 Results of in vitro antioxidant study

The antioxidant activity of different concentration of Apple cider vinegar were studied against DPPH scavenging, nitric oxide scavenging and following observations were recorded.

A) Radical scavenging activity using DPPH

The DPPH radical scavenging activity shown by different concentration of Apple cider vinegar, were found to be concentration dependent. With increase in concentration the radical scavenging activity increased as depicted in **Table 2** and represented graphically in **Figure 1**

Table 2: Results of radical scavenging activity shown by different concentration of Apple cider vinegar.

S. No.	Type of test sample/ Standard	Conc. µg/ml	Percentage inhibition (%I)	IC ₅₀ (µg/ml)
1	ACV (10%)	100	30.62±0.248	197.35
		200	37.27±0.244	
		300	44.19±0.202	
		400	55.33±0.312	
		500	69.55±0.294	
2	ACV (20%)	100	40.35±0.554	138.27
		200	49.12±0.079	
		300	63.85±0.127	
		400	71.02±0.253	
		500	79.91±0.096	
3	ACV (40%)	100	50.35±0.754	108.27
		200	52.12±0.069	
		300	64.85±0.117	
		400	73.02±0.183	
		500	82.91±0.086	
4	Standard Ascorbic acid	100	46.9±0.267	78.49
		200	58.48±0.220	
		300	69.59±0.205	
		400	76.38±0.107	
		500	87.06±0.067	

Figure 1: Graph showing IC₅₀ value of DPPH radical inhibition assay for different concentration of Apple cider vinegar and ascorbic acid as standard.

DPPH scavenging activity increased with increase in concentration for both standard and different concentration of Apple Cider Vinegar Percentage scavenging activity at 100 µg/ml of standard ascorbic acid was found to be 46.9% which increased up to 87.06% at 500 µg/ml. The concentration of apple cider vinegar had the highest DPPH scavenging activity (82.91% at 500 µg/ml). At 500 µg/ml, of 10% concentration of apple cider vinegar has maximum percentage scavenging activity was 69.55%. The IC₅₀ value for the standard was 78.49 µg/ml, while the values for the different concentration of apple cider vinegar were 108.27 µg/ml, 138.27 µg/ml and 197.35 µg/ml, respectively.

B) Reducing Power

The reducing capacity of the different concentration of Apple cider vinegar, another significant indicator of antioxidant activity was also found to be appreciable for all the different concentration of Apple cider vinegar. The reducing power capability of different concentration of Apple cider vinegar and ascorbic acid as standard is shown in **Table 3**.

Table 3: Reducing power assay of different concentration of Apple cider vinegar and Ascorbic acid as standard.

S. No.	Concentration µg/ml	Absorbance measured at 700 nm			
		ACV (10%)	ACV (20%)	ACV (40%)	Standard (Ascorbic acid)
1	100	0.205±0.005	0.281±0.004	0.321±0.003	0.364±.003
2	200	0.387±0.003	0.409±0.006	0.489±0.007	0.548±0.003

3	300	0.482±0.005	0.575±0.006	0.645±0.007	0.753±.001
4	400	0.595±0.003	0.706±0.002	0.809±0.002	0.908±.002
5	500	0.707±0.008	0.933±0.013	0.943±0.013	0.987±0.001

Both the standard and sample concentration' absorbance rose as concentration increased in the reducing power assay. When compared to the standard, reducing power was found to be lower for all three different concentrations of apple cider vinegar decreasing power compounds are electron donors that can function as main and secondary antioxidants by decreasing the oxidized intermediates of lipid peroxidation processes.

B) Nitric Oxide scavenging activity

The nitric oxide radical scavenging activity shown by different concentration of Apple cider vinegar was found to be concentration dependent. With increase in concentration the radical scavenging activity increased as depicted in **Table 4** and represented graphically in **Figure 2**

Table 4: Results of NO inhibition activity (%) of different concentration of Apple cider vinegar and ascorbic acid as standard.

S. No.	Type of test sample/std.	Conc. (µg/ml)	Abs. (nm)	Percentage inhibition (%I)	IC ₅₀ (µg/ml)
1	ACV (10%)	100	0.582	24.76±0.063	344.17
		200	0.481	37.52±0.361	
		300	0.408	45.97±0.198	
		400	0.339	57.89±0.131	
		500	0.239	71.27±0.235	
2	ACV(20%)	100	0.568	24.89±0.104	297.52
		200	0.468	35.37±0.371	
		300	0.387	46.13±0.124	
		400	0.311	54.13±0.137	
		500	0.207	67.55±0.031	
3	ACV(40%)	100	0.488	24.99±0.234	187.52
		200	0.378	32.37±0.373	
		300	0.287	49.13±0.104	
		400	0.281	53.13±0.102	
		500	0.197	75.55±0.081	
4	Standard Ascorbic acid	100	0.352	52.26±0.547	68.31
		200	0.274	62.03±0.321	
		300	0.211	71.65±0.076	
		400	0.147	80.19±0.072	
		500	0.089	88.03±0.122	

Figure 2: Graph showing IC₅₀ value of NO inhibition assay for different concentration of Apple cider vinegar and ascorbic acid as standard.

Different concentration of apple cider vinegar (10%, 20%, 40%) and normal ascorbic acid's ability to scavenge nitric oxide radicals was dose-dependent. The IC₅₀ values for different concentration of apple cider vinegar are 187.52 µg/ml, 297.52 µg/ml, 344.17 µg/ml, and 68.31 µg/ml, respectively. Antioxidant molecules may be the cause of the activity.

3.3 Antibacterial activity of different concentration of Apple cider vinegar. (Disc Diffusion Assay)

The potential antibacterial activity of the different concentration of Apple cider vinegar was initially determined by the disc diffusion approach, and then MICs were calculated from results as described in Table 5 for different concentration of Apple cider vinegar.

Table 5: Antibacterial activity (zone of inhibition) of different concentration of Apple cider vinegar against *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *P.vulgaris* and *S.typhi* bacteria.

Bacterial strains	Test Sample/standard	Conc. (µg/ml)	Zone of Inhibition (mm)
<i>E. coli</i>	ACV(10%)	50	11.5±0.167
		100	13.2±0.167
		200	16.8±0.332
	ACV(20%)	50	12.2±0.226
		100	17.5±0.331
		200	18.3±0.197
	ACV(40%)	50	15.2±0.336
		100	18.5±0.421
		200	20.3±0.287
		Streptomycin disc	10 µg

<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	ACV(10%)	50	12.1±0.315
		100	14.3 ±0.332
		200	16.2±0.302
	ACV(20%)	50	13.6±0.332
		100	16.8±0.238
		200	17.9±0.259
	ACV(40%)	50	14.6±0.452
		100	18.8±0.338
		200	20.5±0.249
Streptomycin disc	10 µg	24.2±0.801	
<i>P. vulgaris</i>	ACV(10%)	50	12.2±0.389
		100	13.7±0.179
		200	14.6±0.151
	ACV(20%)	50	13.8±0.146
		100	15.4±0.161
		200	16.7±0.269
	ACV(40%)	50	14.8±0.136
		100	18.4±0.151
		200	20.7±0.379
Streptomycin disc	10 µg	22.7±0.881	
<i>S .typhi</i>	ACV(10%)	50	13.8±0.566
		100	14.7±0.159
		200	17.6±0.230
	ACV(20%)	50	14.9±0.209
		100	15.8±0.337
		200	18.9±0.235
	ACV(40%)	50	15.9±0.249
		100	16.8±0.447
		200	20.9±0.345
Streptomycin disc	10 µg	24.1±0.830	

Figure 3: Comparison of zone of inhibition of different test organisms using (10%) concentration of Apple cider vinegar with standard drug.

Figure 4: Comparison of zone of inhibition of different test organisms using (20%) concentration of Apple cider vinegar with standard drug.

Figure 5: Comparison of zone of inhibition of different test organisms using (40%) concentration of Apple cider vinegar with standard drug.

Apple cider vinegar of different concentration shown antibacterial efficacy against *Proteus vulgaris*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in the current investigation. When compared to the conventional antibiotic streptomycin (10 µg/ml), the apple cider vinegar concentration-dependent antibacterial activity was caused by the action of apple cider vinegar at doses of 50, 100, and 200 µg/ml. Four Gram-negative bacteria were used to investigate the antibacterial activity of the different concentration of apple cider vinegar. All of the examined bacterial strains were successfully combated by the apple cider

vinegar. *Salmonella typhi*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were all prevented from growing by the apple cider vinegar.

The composition of apple cider vinegar, which are mixtures of phytoconstituents that may affect the diffusion power of the active constituents, and the varying degrees of intrinsic tolerance of test strains to antimicrobials, which can vary MIC values from isolate to isolate, have been found to have a significant impact on the relationship between zone of inhibition and MIC values.

4. CONCLUSION

One of the biggest issues facing medical research is the growing resistance of germs to numerous synthetic antimicrobial drugs. Several studies have identified natural sources of bioactive antibacterial components, like apple cider vinegar (ACV). According to the study's findings, apple cider vinegar contains strong antibacterial properties that could help treat a number of bacterial and fungal diseases. Overall, the study offers strong proof of apple cider vinegar's antimicrobial and antioxidant properties. However, more thorough research is needed to fully comprehend its mode of action and pinpoint the precise bioactive substances causing these effects, which could aid in the creation of innovative natural antimicrobial formulations.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

DPPH = 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl

IC50 = Inhibitory concentration 50%

INT = p-iodonitrotetrazolium chloride

MHA = Muller-Hinton Agar

MIC = Minimum inhibitory concentration

NO = Nitric oxide

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